

21NRM06 EMC-STD

D1: Report on in situ grid impedance characterisation in the frequency range of 30 Hz – 30 MHz including: i) grid impedance measurement methods; ii) influence of the grid impedance variation on the measured conducted emissions, both in common mode and in differential mode, and iii) all the impedance data collected from the harsh environments, iv) new conducted emission method based on impedance measurement with the target uncertainty of 6 dB maximum

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Abbreviations

AMN	Artificial Mains Network
ASD	Adjustable Speed Drive
At	Ampere turns
CISPR	Comité International Spécial des Perturbations Radioélectriques
CM	Common Mode
DM	Differential Mode
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EUT	Equipment Under Test
EV	Electric Vehicle
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
LISN	Line Impedance Stabilization Network
SA	Spectrum Analyzer
SMPS	Switch Mode Power Supply
TUBITAK	Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
VNA	Vector network analyser
RF	Radio frequency

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1. Introduction

Although the International Special Committee on Radio Interference (CISPR) provides in-situ emission test methods in CISPR 11 [1], these procedures exhibit a high measurement uncertainty—up to 25 dB—primarily due to the variability of grid impedance across the frequency spectrum [2]. To address these limitations, a new standard, CISPR 37 Ed. 1.0, is under development. The working group CISPR/CIS/B/WG7 was established to develop this standard [3]. Despite several efforts by European metrology projects to support in-situ testing [4]–[6], their influence on standardization has been limited. This document includes the results and methods for differential mode live impedance and in-situ conducted emission measurement methods in the 30 Hz – 150 kHz frequency range and differential mode and common mode methods in the 150 kHz – 30 MHz frequency range.

2 kHz to 150 kHz range—commonly referred to as supraharmonics—have been shown to cause a variety of disturbances, including inaccuracies in smart meters, audible noise, performance degradation in electrical equipment, and errors in power line communication systems. Devices with power conversion functionality, such as inverters, motor drives, and (electric vehicle) EV chargers, are common sources of supraharmonic emissions. In recent years, there has been growing interest in supraharmonics research, particularly in relation to photovoltaic systems and fast-charging stations, due to their increasing deployment [7]–[16]. Additionally, railway applications are reportedly becoming more affected by supraharmonic emissions [17], [18]. Even residential and office environments are not immune enough to disturbances impacting residual current devices and low-voltage transformers [19]–[25].

One of the primary challenges in in-situ emission measurements is the strong dependence on grid impedance. Laboratory-based measurements typically use (line impedance stabilization network) LISNs to provide a controlled impedance, but for in-situ tests—where LISNs are often not feasible—measurements are usually conducted using voltage and/or current probes [1]. These methods lack standardized impedance control, making the results highly dependent on the grid's unknown and variable impedance. Furthermore, conventional LISNs do not maintain a 50-ohm impedance at frequencies below several hundred kHz, further complicating low-frequency measurements. While some special LISNs and modifications have been proposed, none have been formally incorporated into existing standards, thus limiting the repeatability of measurements unless the grid impedance is known—which introduces yet another technical challenge [26]–[28].

In this project, for conducted emission testing, the frequency range of 100 Hz-150 kHz has been extensively researched, and novel measurement methods have been developed. A precise correlation between the reference and complex test environments have been established based on the accurate live impedance measurements, which has never been performed before with current probes in this frequency range [29-32]. For the live impedance measurement methods, a compact impedance measurement device equipped with current probes thus providing galvanic isolation from live conductors, an integrated small-sized (vector network analyser) VNA (Omicron Bode-100) have been developed. RF amplifier also has been used as an option where VNAs cannot provide enough power in order to increase the dynamic range of the system.

In addition, as a novel further step to the frequency range of 150 kHz – 30 MHz, time domain techniques and phase information have also been included in the established radio frequency (RF) correlation to increase the accuracy and lower the uncertainty in the frequency range of 150 kHz – 30 MHz. The proposed use of time-domain measurement methods in conjunction with mains and EUT impedance characterisation will allow the reduction of the previously reported in situ uncertainty values of up to 25 dB towards the maximum 6 dB target found at conventional electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) test laboratories.

2. Methodology and experiments

This section describes the theoretical background of the live impedance measurement methods, setups and the procedures followed.

In this study, impedance and conducted emission measurements are investigated in three frequency ranges.

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Table 1. Impedance and emission ranges

Harmonics	Supraharmonics	Conducted emission
100 Hz – 2 kHz	2 kHz – 150 kHz	150 kHz – 30 MHz

For the sake of simplicity and ease of measurement methods, frequency range is divided into three parts. Different setups have been used for each frequency range.

2.1 Harmonics range (100 Hz – 2 kHz)

This method is defined as V-I (Voltage-Current) method and the measurement setup is built upon the CE101 and CS101 test setups defined in MIL-STD 461G [33]. The CE101 test defined in the standard MIL-STD461G is applied to military and aerospace equipment. This test is performed to measure low frequency emissions from supply ports of the Equipment Under Test (EUT) in the 30 Hz - 10 kHz range. First, the CE101 test requires a calibration process performed on a known resistive load to verify the test bench. During this calibration, a simple circuit shown in Fig. 1 (a) is set to produce a known current through the reference resistor at the frequencies stated by the standard. Thereafter, the known current on the circuit is measured by the CE101 test system and it is checked whether the system yields the expected results. If the deviation between the known and measured current is greater than ± 3 dB, the system is out of tolerance and cannot be used. In the test stage, current emissions from the EUT are measured with a current probe and a frequency-selective receiver, as shown in Fig. 1 (b).

Fig. 1. CE101, (a) calibration setup, (b) test setup.

To analyse the influence of the source impedance on the measurement circuit and alleviate the uncertainty and the discrepancies arising from the test circuit impedance, it is firstly measured the live loop impedance of the measurement circuit, which includes the EUT, LISNs, chamber filters, power supply and cables, in different source conditions. For the live impedance measurement, CS101 test system was utilised whose calibration and test setups are depicted in Fig. 2. The CS101 test is a low frequency immunity test which is considered the counterpart of the CE101. During the CS101 test low frequency sinusoidal voltage ripples are injected to power ports of the EUT in the range from 30 Hz to 150 kHz, as investigated in detail in [34-39]. Here, CS101 test system has been improved with a complementary current measurement feature in addition to the intrinsic voltage measurement. As a result, the CS101 test system was adapted for impedance measurements.

In addition, a post-processing Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) - based time domain solution has been integrated to separate injected ripples from the AC power frequency of the EUT and to facilitate accurate live impedance measurements under adverse grid or EUT supply voltage conditions. The integration of the FFT analysis into

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CS101 testing and the details of FFT analysis can be found in detail in [40-44]. Alternatively, integrated FFT features of oscilloscopes can be used instead of the post-processing for expediting the process if it is available on the oscilloscope and a proper FFT-activated instrument driver exists on the used CS101 test software.

Fig. 2. CS101, (a) calibration setup, (b) test setup.

Finally, the test circuit loop impedance deviations were calculated, by using the setup and equation given in Fig. 3 and in (1) respectively, considered as correction factors between different low frequency test environments and compared them with loop current deviations to verify the proposed method.

$$Z_{loop} = \frac{V}{I} \quad (1)$$

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Fig. 3. CE 101 test system along with FFT and current measurement enabled CS101 system used for impedance measurement.

Any EUT can be modelled as a combination of a constant voltage source and an internal impedance (Thevenin equivalent). This model is used to analyse the measurement and alleviate the uncertainty arising from the test circuit impedance. As common mode (CM) currents are not expected in this low frequency range, analysis has been limited only to the differential mode (DM), and the relevant circuit diagram is given in Fig. 4 for the differential mode.

Fig. 4. DM circuit model for low frequency conducted emission.

In this context, The CE101 test system, along with the live impedance measurement setup utilising the FFT-enabled CS101 test system, is depicted in Fig. 3. The first channel of the oscilloscope with 1 MΩ input impedance is dedicated to voltage measurements whereas the second channel of the oscilloscope with 50 Ω input impedance is assigned to current measurements. For current measurements, 50 Ω input of the oscilloscope was used, because the current probe factors are generally calibrated to be used along with 50 Ω matched instruments, such as a measuring receiver. Alternatively, current measurements may be accomplished with a separate frequency-selective instrument. In this measurement system, the total loop impedance of the CE101 test circuit, which involves the EUT, source and cable impedance values together (see Fig. 3), is targeted instead of separate EUT or source impedance values. The loop impedance is detected by the ratio of the voltage measured across the coupling transformer to the measured loop current as presented in (2) to be used in the calculation of the correction factor (K) as given in (3), which is expected to establish a link between different test environments. Here, $Z_{CE101_reference_loop}$ is the impedance of the test circuit selected as reference, and $Z_{CE101_test_loop}$ is the loop impedance measured in the targeted emission measurement setup under investigation. $Z_{CE101_reference_loop}$ and $Z_{CE101_test_loop}$ include the impedance of the EUT, power source, and other components, e.g., LISNs, filters, and cables. The correction factor is also known as impedance deviation.

$$K = \frac{Z_{CE101_reference_loop}}{Z_{CE101_test_loop}} \quad (2)$$

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Then, the emission level ($I_{CE101_reference_loop}$) in the reference circuit can be linked to the emission level ($I_{CE101_test_loop}$) in the targeted circuit by using the measured impedance deviation as given by (3),

$$I_{CE101_test_loop} = I_{CE101_reference_loop} \times K \quad (3)$$

Alternatively, emission results obtained in different test environments may be scaled to a predefined load such as 50Ω by using the measured loop impedance values as given in (4) and (5). This can be convenient to harmonize emission results obtained from different test environments and make them comparable between each other.

$$I_{scaled_current} = I_{CE101_test_loop} \times S \quad (4)$$

In this case, the scaling factor S can be defined as follows;

$$S = \frac{Z_{CE101_test_loop}}{50 \Omega} \quad (5)$$

The current probe in the setup shown in Fig. 1 has two functions. One of them is to detect the current required for the live impedance measurement and the other is to perform current measurements required for conducted emission testing. After the loop impedance measurement, the coupling transformer is removed from the circuit for the conducted emission testing. This is made because the measured loop impedance only includes the emission measurement circuit not the coupling transformer. The removal of the coupling transformer is simply attained by short circuiting the output of the coupling transformer just before the emission measurement after the loop impedance measurement. After the loop impedance measurement, the succeeding step is calculating correction factors. The verification of correction factors is performed by means of measuring loop currents, considered as emission results, in the same test environment and comparing loop current deviations with impedance deviations. The good consistency between the loop impedance and current deviations is expected to verify the proposed method.

A piece of software has been developed by using LabWindows/CVI in order to perform impedance measurements based on the CS101 test system and carry out FFT-based time domain processing to measure voltage and current values under the adverse AC EUT power frequency. The same software is also able to perform conducted emission measurement after the impedance measurement.

The impedance measurement method was verified by using lumped elements with known impedance as test subjects, specifically, 0.5Ω , 50Ω , $80 \mu\text{F}$, $430 \mu\text{H}$. Next, three types of EUT were employed to verify that the proposed conducted emission measurement method improved with the impedance measurement. One of them was a signal generator RF output to verify the method in nearly ideal conditions. For the simulation of source impedance diversity, an assortment of impedance values (50Ω , $80 \mu\text{F}$, $430 \mu\text{H}$) behind the LISNs were employed, and they were directly connected to the power source side of the LISNs (see Fig. 5). The other EUT was a homemade harmonic reference device which is designed as a square wave generator. As the harmonic reference device was a standalone device and it does not require direct supply voltage coming from LISNs to operate, a variety of resistors (50Ω as the reference, 26.6Ω , 13.3Ω and 6.6Ω) were directly connected to the output of the device as seen in Fig. 6 to create different dummy source impedance values with respect to 50Ω . After these preliminary measurements with the predictable devices, finally, an uncontrolled device, an Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) as the EUT, was tested in an actual conducted emission measurement setup (see Fig. 7). A clean power supply (Schaffner, NSG 1007-45) providing the EUT with 220 VAC, 50 Hz, together with a variety of combinations of two in-house chamber filters and a commercial chamber filter (ETS, Model: N5007), is used behind the LISNs at the power source side to supply the UPS and create different source impedance situations. Different source situations were created through the inclusion and removal of the chamber filters. As the chamber filters between the LISNs and the power supply were likely to influence the source impedance, they were very instrumental in changing the source impedance. The UPS was tested on 6 different scenarios in aggregate as given and depicted in Table 2. As the UPS was predominantly emitting only in the range of 30 Hz - 2 kHz, its test and analysis were stopped at 2 kHz, and proceeding beyond 2 kHz

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was unnecessary whereas the signal generator RF output and harmonic reference device were tested and analysed in the entire CE101 frequency range (30 Hz – 10 kHz). In addition, for scenario 5 and scenario 6, which include multiple chamber filters, frequency range was confined to around 1 kHz because the harmonics start to become very low and unusable beyond 1 kHz for analysis and calculation due to the inclusion of more than one chamber filter. In an attempt to stoke up the harmonics and increase the sensitivity beyond 1 kHz in the use of two chamber filters in series, the UPS was also supplied with 300 VAC instead of 220 VAC and repeated the measurement for the scenario 6. Lastly, in order not to clutter the paper with too many graphs, corresponding absolute impedance and current values are given, which produce the deviations shown in the graphs, only for one case of the UPS, not for all the test cases.

Fig. 5. Conducted emission measurement setup installed with resistors, capacitors and inductors as source impedance simulation and the signal generator RF output as EUT.

Fig. 6. Conducted emission measurement setup installed with the harmonic reference device as EUT.

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Fig. 7. CE 101 test setup installed with the UPS as EUT.

Table 2.UPS Measurement Scenarios

Scenarios	Measurement Setup
1	EUT — LISN — Supply
2	EUT — LISN — Commercial Filter — Supply
3	EUT — LISN — In-House Filter1 — Supply
4	EUT — LISN — In-House Filter2 — Supply
5	EUT — LISN — Commercial Filter — In-House Filter1 — Supply
6	EUT — LISN — In-House Filter1 — In-House Filter2 — Supply

After the installation of the required setups, the loop impedance measurements were completed for each of them. The frequencies, at which the impedance measurement was performed, were decided through a preliminary and quick emission test just before the impedance measurement. The preliminary emission check gave us peak values and frequencies for the impedance measurement. In order not to get in conflict with the EUT emission frequencies during the impedance measurement, each detected EUT emission frequency was slightly shifted left and right and these revised frequencies were recorded for the impedance measurement. For example, if a device emits at 150 Hz, 450 Hz, 850 Hz, 1.15 kHz, 1.55 kHz, 1.95 kHz, impedance measurements should be carried out at 120 Hz, 180 Hz, 420 Hz, 480 Hz, 820 Hz, 880 Hz, 1.120 kHz, 1.180 kHz, 1.52 kHz, 1.58 kHz, 1.92 kHz, 1.98 kHz in order not to collide with the EUT emission frequencies but also to be close to them for more accurate impedance measurements and correction factors calculated in (2).

The verification results of the impedance measurement system are presented in Fig. 8. As observed in Fig. 8, the impedance measurement system yields acceptable agreement that proves its trustworthiness. In this simple verification, as the reference values, we directly used the rated values of 0.5 Ω and 50 Ω whereas we used the rated values and the theoretical impedance equations of the capacitor (80 μF) and the inductor (430 μH).

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Fig. 8. Impedance measurement verification with (a) the 0.5 Ω resistor, (b) the 50 Ω terminator, (c) the 80 μF capacitor, (d) the 430 μH inductor.

Fig. 9. Impedance and loop current deviations for the signal generator RF output used as EUT between the different source impedance conditions (a) 50 Ω versus 80 μF, (b) 50 Ω versus 430 μH, (c) 80 μF versus 430 μF.

After the impedance verification, the loop current and impedance deviation results of the signal generator RF output used as a dummy EUT in different source impedance conditions are given in Fig. 9. As clearly observed in Fig. 9, although the impedance results are significantly distinct in different source environments, the loop current deviation acceptably follows the loop impedance deviation per graph, which verifies the proposed method in an ideal test environment. In each graph, the impedance deviation signifies the difference in loop impedance magnitudes in decibels between two different source impedance conditions while the current deviation shows the same for the loop current flowing in the test circuits. For example, in Fig. 9 (a), while a deviation of 5 dB in loop impedance occurs due to the change of the dummy source impedance condition from

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50 Ω to 80 μF behind the LISNs, the loop current deviates in a similar manner as the loop impedance. The consistent change in both the loop impedance and current deviations may be regarded as a good start for the proposed method. It should be reiterated here that the impedance deviation is in fact the correction factor between the two cases per graph.

Fig. 10. Loop impedance and current deviations with respect to 50 Ω for the source impedance conditions: 6.6 Ω, 13.3 Ω, 26.6 Ω for the harmonic reference device.

In the same vein, the harmonic reference device results are presented in Fig. 10 in the range of 30 Hz – 10 kHz. Again, there is good agreement in the impedance and current deviation results with respect to 50 Ω. When we change the dummy source impedance from 6.6 Ω to 26.6 Ω with irregular steps and compare the results with the 50 Ω results, the loop impedance and current deviation curves change in harmony with each other. To exemplify this, when we change the dummy source impedance from 6.6 Ω to 50 Ω, it yields a deviation of around 14 dB in both the impedance and current values, as seen in Fig. 10. The good agreement in impedance and current deviations also exists in the other impedance transitions from 13.3 Ω and 26.6 Ω to 50 Ω.

Fig. 11. Impedance and loop current deviations with respect to the standard setup (scenario 1) for the UPS supplied by 220 VAC for the source conditions: (a) scenario 2, (b) scenario 3, (c) scenario 4, (d) scenario 5, (e) scenario 6.

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After the preliminary results obtained with the signal generator RF output and harmonic reference source that may be regarded as ideal or dummy EUTs, ultimately the results of the UPS selected as an actual piece of EUT are presented in Fig. 11 - 12. In this step, the standard CE101 test setup (scenario 1) that only comprises the EUT and the LISNs was selected as the reference setup. In this standard setup, the LISNs were directly connected to our clean AC power source without any chamber filters. In all the other conditions (scenarios 2 - 6), the chamber filters were placed between the LISNs and the power supply in order to change the source impedance and create different test conditions. In Fig. 11 (a), we observe that the commercial chamber filter inserted between the LISNs and the power supply in scenario 2 does not markedly change the source impedance and does not produce significant impedance deviation with respect to the standard CE101 test setup. Similarly, the current does not change in the two test conditions. When we study Fig. 11 (b), it is seen that inserting our in-house filter 1 between the LISNs and the power supply in scenario 3 changes the loop impedance of the CE101 test setup. It also causes the loop current to deviate similarly. That means that the loop current can be calculated, also called emission level, in a targeted test environment by just measuring the loop impedance values of the reference and the targeted test environment. In our case here, even if we did not measure the loop current value in the targeted environment (scenario 3), we could estimate it by using the loop current in the reference environment (scenario 1) and the impedance deviation considered as the correction factor calculated in (1). We obtain another good consistency in Fig. 11 (c). The in-house filter 2 inserted between the LISNs and the power supply in scenario 4 produces a deviation quite equivalent to the deviation produced by the in-house filter 1.

Fig. 12. (a) Impedance and loop current deviations with respect to the standard setup (scenario 1) for the UPS supplied by 300 VAC for the source impedance condition: scenario 6, (b) absolute impedance and loop current values which are used for deviation calculation.

When the commercial and in-house filters are placed in series between the LISNs and the power supply in scenario 5, it produces an impedance deviation visually alike to scenarios 3 & 4 but with a higher deviation at higher frequencies. As clearly seen in Fig. 11 (d), even at 1.3 kHz, the impedance deviation in scenario 5 reaches -6 dB but we were not able to record the harmonic currents beyond 1.3 kHz as they become very low and useless with the insertion of the two chamber filters in series. In Fig. 11 (e), a similar graph is obtained when the in-house filter 1 and in-house filter 2 are placed in series between the LISNs and the power supply in scenario 6. Also, here the frequency range had to be limited to 1.1 kHz as the magnitudes of the harmonics sagged significantly beyond 1.1 kHz. Finally, the results of the UPS supplied by 300 VAC instead of 220 VAC in an attempt to strengthen the harmonics are shown in Fig. 12 (a) along with the absolute impedance and current values in Fig. 12 (b) just for information. When the supply voltage is increased from 220 VAC to 300 VAC, the strength of the harmonics seems to increase but the stability of the harmonics seems to worsen. As a result, as seen in Fig. 12 (a), when the supply voltage is increased to 300 VAC, acceptable harmonics starts to occur up to 2 kHz but with higher fluctuation. This final result shows the effectiveness of the proposed method as the two curves are reasonably following each other in Fig. 12 (a) up to 2 kHz despite the remarkable fluctuation in the harmonic levels.

This study was presented in EMC Europe 2023 Conference [45].

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2.2 Supraharmonics range (2 kHz – 150 kHz)

Measurement in the supraharmonics range were performed with the VNA method. This method utilizes a VNA in order to measure the live grid and the EUT impedance via current probes. After measuring the impedance values, an interference measurement device (EMI receiver or a digitizer) measures the emission in current form. Since VNAs are expensive and sensitive, a light and portable VNA (Omicron Bode 100) was incorporated. Nevertheless, for grids with high ambient noise, output of the VNAs are insufficient in lower frequencies and cannot exceed the noise levels in the grid. To avoid this obstacle, VNAs can be equipped with an RF amplifier and the signal injected into the measurement circuit can be amplified. The impedance measurement setup is simply shown in Fig. 13 and based on the calculations given in (1) – (4).

Fig. 13. Impedance measurement setup using VNA and current probes.

$$\frac{V_{p1}}{V_{p2}} = \frac{S_{11}+1}{S_{21}} \quad (6)$$

$$R_{std} = K \left(\frac{V_{p1}}{V_{p2}} \right) \Big|_{Z_x=R_{std}} - Z_{setup} \quad (7)$$

$$0 = K \left(\frac{V_{p1}}{V_{p2}} \right) \Big|_{Z_x=short} - Z_{setup} \quad (8)$$

$$Z_x = K \left(\frac{V_{p1}}{V_{p2}} \right) - Z_{setup} \quad (9)$$

Where, K is a coefficient and V_{p1}/V_{p2} is the value based on S_{11} and S_{12} parameters for each of three conditions; short circuit, precision known impedance and unknown impedance at a-a' port. R_{std} is the known reference impedance, Z_x is the unknown impedance and the Z_{setup} is the impedance of the setup loop [46].

Experience show that differential mode currents are dominant in the frequency range of 2 kHz – 150 kHz, so no common-mode measurements were performed in this range. Based on VNA method, DM impedance measurement setup is shown Fig.14 and in Fig.15.

Measurement system is compound of a Omicron Bode 100 Vector Network Analyzer, FCC F73 current probes, Amplifier Research 150Watt Amplifier, pulse limiters and RF limiters. The system is equipped with a software developed on Labwindows/CVI programming platform. A screenshot from the impedance measurement software is given in Fig. 16. After a short-open-reference calibration based on equations (6)-(9), the system is ready to measure any unknown impedance. The software is also compatible to operate with Keysight E5601B VNA.

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Fig. 14. DM impedance measurement of LISN system/Mains together with EUT

Fig. 15. DM impedance measurement system of mains together with EUT

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Fig. 16. Impedance measurement software

First, impedance measurement system was verified via known impedance values. A set of passive components were measured; e.g. 50 ohms, 300 ohms, 0.5 ohms and 1uH. Measurement system satisfies the impedance value tolerance stated as %20 in CISPR 16-1-2 standard [47]. Verification results are given in Fig. 17.

For impedance measurements, it is crucial to determine the output power and the resolution bandwidth (RBW) of the VNA. There is a trade-off between the measurement time and RBW; so that if the ambient noise is higher than the signal injected to the measurement circuit, decreasing the RBW down to 5-10 Hz. In supraharmonics range, RBW was selected as 10 Hz. In 2 kHz – 10 kHz range VNA output was set at 0 dBm. This power is also attenuated before amplifier input to protect the amplifier. Briefly adjusting the VNA output is depending on the ambient noise in the grid. So a pre-scan of the ambient measurement with an EMI receiver/spectrum analyser is strongly recommended before the impedance measurement. Also, all configurations on the software should be kept during short-open-reference and unknown measurements.

(a)

(b)

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(c)

(d)

Fig. 17 (a) 50 ohms measurement result, (b) 0.5 ohm verification result, (c) 300 ohms verifications result, (d) 1uH verification result

2.3 Grid impedance in supraharmonics range (2 kHz – 150 kHz)

Second, grid impedances were measured in three different locations. 4uF capacitor replaced as an EUT in order to provide high impedance to 50 Hz and low impedance to supraharmonics range. Short-open-reference calibration of the impedance measurement system was performed with 4uF connected to the grid via the current probes and the DM fixture. DM grid impedance measurement setup is shown in Fig. 18.

An ordinary laboratory mains in TUBITAK, conference hall in a TUBITAK facility and a rural area in Turkey were selected. These locations are selected from different points of the grid fed by different transformers in order to see how different feeder conditions effect the grid impedance. Results are presented in Fig. 19. And measurement locations are presented in Fig. 20.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 18 (a) Grid impedance measurement at laboratory mains (b) DM fixture with probes

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Fig. 19 (a) three different locations impedance magnitude comparison (b) three different locations impedance phase comparison

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 20 (a) Laboratory measurement site (b) conference hall measurement site (c) Rural area measurement site

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It is seen that especially after 10 kHz, there is a significant deviation between different measurement locations. This is expected due to large deviation in terms of variety of connected devices to the grid. Besides, switching frequency of the devices connected to the mains may cause impedance variations because deviation start from almost 10 kHz. It is commonly known that devices like photovoltaic inverters, adjustable speed drives of electric motors incorporate switching elements operating in this frequency range. This can be interpreted as these devices affect the grid impedance due to their switching functions.

In addition, grid impedance of the laboratory mains were measured at 4 different hours of a day: 01.00, 09.00, 13.00, and 20.00. No significant changes in the impedance were observed during the measurements. Results are given in Fig. 21. It is interpreted as there are not many load changes on the transformer feeding the laboratory mains during the measurement hours of a day.

Fig. 21. (a) Impedance magnitude at 4 different hours of a day (b) impedance phase at 4 different hours of a day

Finally, advantages of this impedance measurement system can be listed as follows:

- 1) Measurement system is not a closed box, it is free to install from scratch. All the equipment used in this research are commercially available. User only needs to develop his/her own software, or make an excel file, according to the used VNA. So the system is open to improvement.
- 2) Second, since the current probes are physically isolated from the high voltage/current carrying wires, user is protected from hazardous voltages.
- 3) In case of in-situ measurements, the measurement system can be powered via a 1000 Watt uninterruptible power supply (UPS) (dimensions are same as a desktop PC), so that the measurements are not affected by the impedance of the RF amplifier and power adapter of the VNA.

2.4 New emission test method based on impedance measurement in supraharmonics range (2 kHz – 150 kHz)

In laboratory conditions, conducted emission is measured using LISNs. However, when it is not possible to use LISNs for some reason (very large EUTs, high power that LISNs cannot handle, etc.) current or voltage probe can be used. The proposed method is based on measured impedance of EUT and the grid, then the conducted emission via current probes. Thus the method decreases the measurement uncertainty from 25 dB

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to 6 dB by eliminating the grid impedance dependency of emission results and provides safe measurement in in-situ conditions by isolating the high current cables from the personnel. The principle is to establish a correlation between standard test circuit impedance (LISN+EUT impedance) and the in-situ emission measurement circuit impedance (mains+EUT) thus obtain correction factors. Then these factors can be applied to emission measurement results to obtain laboratory condition results.

The circuit model of conducted emission measurements for DM in laboratory environment is presented in Fig. 21. As seen in Fig.22, the interference source inside the EUT is indicated as V_{EUT_DM} for DM circuit model. Z_{EUT_DM} is the internal impedance of the EUT DM circuit model. Z_{SETUP_DM} is the impedance of the used cables including used measurement components such as current probes. The figure shows the reference setup installed with two LISNs in laboratory environment. The impedance of each used LISN is depicted as 50 ohm. The each LISN impedance becomes series in the DM model [48]. This method was proposed for 150 kHz – 30 MHz conducted emission measurements however, 2 kHz – 150 kHz range has never been investigated before.

Fig. 22. Circuit model of conducted emission measurements in (a) laboratory environment for DM circuit model (b) in-situ for DM circuit model

For reference DM model, the flowing DM current and the induced DM voltage just at the LISN system in Fig. 22 (a) is depicted as I_{DM_REF} and V_{DM_REF} respectively. I_{DM_REF} and V_{DM_REF} are simply calculated as given in (10) and (11).

$$I_{DM_REF} = \frac{V_{EUT_DM}}{Z_{EUT_DM} + Z_{SETUP_DM} + Z_{LISN_DM}} \quad (10)$$

$$V_{DM_REF} = \frac{Z_{LISN_DM} * V_{EUT_DM}}{Z_{EUT_DM} + Z_{SETUP_DM} + Z_{LISN_DM}} \quad (11)$$

On the other hand, unlike the laboratory environment, the method for in-situ has the circuit model shown in Fig. 22 (b). Currents and voltages are based on the impedance of mains instead of the reference LISN impedance, so that the equations for in-situ can be given as follows in (12) and (13) DM current and voltages.

$$I_{DM} = \frac{V_{EUT_DM}}{Z_{EUT_DM} + Z_{SETUP_DM} + Z_{MAINS_DM}} \quad (12)$$

$$V_{DM} = \frac{Z_{MAINS_DM} * V_{EUT_DM}}{Z_{EUT_DM} + Z_{SETUP_DM} + Z_{MAINS_DM}} \quad (13)$$

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As seen in the equations (10) - (13), the only difference between the reference setup and the alternative setup is the mains impedance instead of the reference LISN impedance for DM currents/voltages. Besides, in the equations, the DM voltages/currents are stated with only DM subscripts without “REF” in order to emphasize that these are industrial currents not the reference one of the laboratory environment. Finally, all the impedance measurements lead to correction factors between the reference emission setup with the reference LISN and the alternative setup without the reference LISN as given in equations (14) and (15) with the assumption that DM interference sources inside the EUT are constant.

$$K_{\text{Current_DM}} = \frac{I_{\text{DM_REF}}}{I_{\text{DM}}} = \frac{Z_{\text{EUT_DM}} + Z_{\text{SETUP_DM}} + Z_{\text{MAINS_DM}}}{Z_{\text{EUT_DM}} + Z_{\text{SETUP_DM}} + Z_{\text{LISN_DM}}} \quad (14)$$

$$K_{\text{Voltage_DM}} = \frac{V_{\text{DM_REF}}}{V_{\text{DM}}} = K_{\text{Current_DM}} \cdot \frac{Z_{\text{LISN_DM}}}{Z_{\text{MAINS_DM}}} \quad (15)$$

Based on the principle introduced above, emission of an electric motor driven by an adjustable speed drive (ASD) is measured with standard setup (with LISN) and with mains. Setup with LISN and setup without LISN are depicted in Fig. 23 (a) and fig. 23 (b) respectively. As seen in in Fig. 24, deviation between emission measurements with peak and average detectors are in agreement with impedance change.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 23. (a) Emission measurement setup with LISNs, (b) emission measurement setup without LISN

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Fig. 24 Correlation between impedance change and emission changes in due to different test environment.

This result proves that, if the emission values of the EUT is not changing significantly in time, impedance and emission values can be correlated. Utilizing this information, one can calculate the laboratory emission values V_{LISN} of an EUT without using LISNs. However, it is noteworthy to exclude the impedance of the current probes and DM fixture Z_{SETUP_DM} before calculating the V_{LISN} . Because in the standard setup, current probes and DM fixture do not exist normally. Consequently, after calculating the theoretical factors based on the impedance measurements, I_{DM} measured in in-situ is linked to I_{DM_REF} in the reference setup and finally the voltage measured at the RF port of one of LISNs is predicted as given in (17). In (17), Z_{SINGLE_LISN} is the DM impedance of a single LISN. In Fig. 25, Laboratory measurement with LISNs and calculated V_{LISN} is compared, it is seen that there is a good agreement between two results. Peak and average detectors were used in order to show the consistency between impedance and emission measurements.

$$V_{LISN} = I_{DM_REF} \times |Z_{DM_LISN}| \quad (17)$$

Fig. 25. 0.75 kW induction motor with ASD, comparison of measured and calculated average and peak measurements.

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It is important to note that, since LISNs and filters are not used in in-situ tests, ambient noise cannot be filtered. For the practical use of the method in in-situ, it is suggested that to measure the ambient noise before the measurements. If the ambient noise is too high, use of an isolation transformer suggested, if available. If it is not possible to use an isolation transformer or ambient noise is too high even with an isolation transformer, which means the noise in the grid caused by the EUT will be much lower than the noise generated by other devices connected to the grid. In this case, if the EUT will only be used in the test location (normally this is so, that's why the EUT is measured in-situ) the measurement results will make sense under these conditions, for compliance evaluation. In Fig. 24, some measurement points were not evaluated because of the same reason. Especially significant higher ambient noise levels are detected between 7 kHz and 14 kHz, and between 22 kHz and 35 kHz. So these emission values are taken into consideration. Another EUT, a switch mode power supply (SMPS) was chosen. Test setup and the good agreement between the calculated and the measured emission values in Fig. 26 and Fig. 27 respectively. This device is designed as reference emission source and consists of an SMPS loaded with a linear resistor.

Fig. 26. SMPS measurement setup

Fig. 27. Comparison of measured and calculated average and peak measurements.

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Additionally, care should be taken for the installation of the setup with current probes. Current probes should be capable of handling the measured currents and saturation is a very important issue for the probes. In this study, several types of commercially available probes have been studied and advantages and disadvantages were identified. Detailed results from investigation of probes are presented in Table 2. A detailed investigation on RF current probes are given in Section 2.4. An RF amplifier having a frequency range starting from DC and a non-floating output is suggested. Audio amplifiers may cause reflections to the VNA even if the VNAs are protected with limiters. Power and pulse limiters are strongly recommended in order to protect the VNA from amplified power and possible transients from the mains. In this study VNA's input and output were protected with Keysight 11930A power limiter and an AFJ pulse limiter+20 dB attenuator was added to the input of the VNA.

2.5 150 kHz – 30 MHz range

Conducted emission measurement based on impedance measurement method in 150 kHz – 30 MHz range was previously studied in EURAMET EMRP Project IND60 - Improved EMC test methods in industrial environments [48]. However this research was made only in frequency domain and phase information was not included. To improve the uncertainty of in-situ emission measurement system based on impedance measurement, time domain emission measurement was investigated.

Calculating the emission is same with the supraharmonics range. But in this frequency range; since CM and DM are effective, both modes should be investigated. Circuit for CM is given in Fig. 28. Equations (10)-(13) were presented for DM in the previous section. Likewise, CM equations given in (18)-(21) are the same only with the exception of CM suffix.

Fig. 28. Circuit model of conducted emission measurements in (a) laboratory environment for CM circuit model (b) in-situ for CM circuit model

$$I_{CM_REF} = \frac{V_{EUT_CM}}{Z_{EUT_CM} + Z_{SETUP_CM} + Z_{LISN_CM}} \quad (18)$$

$$V_{CM_REF} = \frac{Z_{LISN_CM} * V_{EUT_CM}}{Z_{EUT_CM} + Z_{SETUP_CM} + Z_{LISN_CM}} \quad (19)$$

$$I_{CM} = \frac{V_{EUT_CM}}{Z_{EUT_CM} + Z_{SETUP_CM} + Z_{MAINS_CM}} \quad (20)$$

$$V_{CM} = \frac{Z_{MAINS_CM} * V_{EUT_CM}}{Z_{EUT_CM} + Z_{SETUP_CM} + Z_{MAINS_CM}} \quad (21)$$

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Table 3. Overview of preferred current probes

	FCC F73	Pearson 8590C	Pearson 5101	Pearson 411	Pearson 5046	R & S EZ-17	PEM Rog. CWT6	LEM Ultrastab 605	DANISENSE DT200ID
full scale current (A _{pk})	350	500	1000	5000	25000	300	1200	850	285
tolerated DC ⁽²⁾ & 50/60 Hz current (A _{rms})	350	DC: see droop 50/60 Hz: 0.05/0.06 ⁽⁴⁾	DC: see droop 50/60 Hz: 0.4/0.48	DC: see droop 50/60 Hz: 35/42	DC: see droop 50/60 Hz: 106/127	DC: 300 AC: 210	DC: see droop 50/60 Hz: in band, see full scale	irrelevant	irrelevant
droop (%/ms)	negligible	700	100	15	0.25	negligible	0.9	irrelevant	irrelevant
bandwidth: low freq 3dB point f_L (Hz) high freq 3dB point f_H (MHz)	100 30	1000 150	150 18	25 20	0.5 20	100 ⁽³⁾ 200	1 10 / 16 ⁽¹⁾	DC 0.3	DC 2
sensitivity (V/A)	1	1	0.5	0.1	0.01	3.1 @ 1 MHz 0.003 @ 1 kHz	0.005	1:1500 turns ratio, 0.15 with 10 Ω load	1:1000 turns ratio, 0.1 with 10 Ω load
output impedance (Ω)	50	50	50	50	50	low & reactive ⁽⁵⁾	50	current source, load resistor	current source, load resistor
output noise (μV/√Hz)	Passive	passive	passive	passive	passive	passive	4.9 (calc over 10 MHz)	1.2 (calc over 50 kHz)	1.8 (calc over 100 kHz)
linearity error %	not given	not given	not given	not given	not given	not given	0.05	< 0.001	< 0.0001
stability: vs. temp., ageing	not given	not given	not given	not given	not given	not given		1 ppm / month	0.1 ppm / month
mechanical features: openable, bore diam. (mm)	yes, 67	yes, 26	yes, 50	yes, 13	no, 12	yes, 30	yes, 90 / 200	no, 30	no, 20

Notes:

- (1) depends on loop length: 16 MHz for standard 300 mm loop, 10 MHz for enlarged 700 mm loop.
- (2) DC / 50 Hz tolerance is a combination of heating and saturation.
- (3) low frequency cutoff f_L estimated from available signal, 300 μV/A.
- (4) inquiry to Pearson for tolerated out-of-band 50/60 Hz; answer not clear, must be tested on each sample, expected increase of immunity, but not able to quantify.
- (5) suitable for current injection, need 50 Ω termination.

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Impedance measurement setups for CM and DM are given in Fig. 29 and Fig. 30 respectively.

Fig. 29. CM impedance measurement of LISN system or Mains together with EUT [48]

Fig. 30. DM impedance measurement of LISN system/Mains together with EUT [48]

Experiences show that ambient noise in this frequency range is generally lower than that with respect to the supraharmonics range. So, it is not mandatory to use an RF amplifier with the VNA. It is even recommended not to use an amplifier because user needs to take too many measures to protect the amplifier and the VNA.

System Verification

First, impedance measurement system was verified with known precision impedance values. A 1 uH and a MIL-STD461G LISN (Solar, 9233-50-TS-50-N) impedance measurements are depicted in Fig. 31 and in Fig. 32 respectively.

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Fig. 31. 1uH impedance measurement compared with the reference value

Fig. 32. MIL-STD 461G LISN (Solar, 9233-50-TS-50-N)

After impedance measurement system was verified, emission and impedance measurements were performed.

It is important to note, adjusted VNA configuration should be kept during short-open-reference and the unknown measurement. Since amplifier was not used in this frequency range, VNA output was selected as 10 dBm in order to maximize the power of the signal injected and so to increase the accuracy of the measurement. RBW was selected as 10 Hz as it was in supraharmonics range.

First, a CM noise generator given in Fig. 33 with a stable noise was tested to verify the proposed method. Comparison of calculated and measured values of the generator is shown in Fig. 34. A good agreement is seen between the measured and the calculated CM values.

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Fig. 33. CM noise generator

Fig. 34. Comparison of measured and calculated LISN voltage for the CM noise generator

After noise generator measurements, real EUT measurements were performed with the ASD+motor combination which was tested before in supraharmonics range.

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Time-domain measurements were performed with emiGO software and Picoscope 5444B Oscilloscope. Time domain setup and the screenshot from the emiGO software are depicted in Fig. 35 (a) and Fig. 35 (b) respectively. CM and DM measurements without LISNs are combined in-line with corresponding impedance values according to (13) and (21) in vector quantities.

Fig. 35. Time domain emission measurement (a) measurement setup (b) software

A good agreement is seen in comparison of measured Peak vs. calculated and the measured Average versus calculated Average values, given in Fig. 36 (a) and Fig. 36 (b) respectively. Since emission values are close to ambient noise between around 9 MHz and 23 MHz, these frequencies are ignored as it was done before in supraharmonics range.

Fig. 36 Comparison of measured and calculated (a) Peak (b) Average

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2.6 Investigation on current probes

Non-linearity and saturation behaviour of RF current probes were investigated under realistic high-current conditions, which are typical in grid impedance and conducted emission measurements. These probes, essential in EMC testing, may exhibit distortion or sensitivity loss when exposed to large DC or AC currents due to magnetic core saturation. The study aims to quantify these effects and explore simple methods to extend probe usability in high-current environments. Distortion and frequency response of RF current probes under DC/AC bias currents up to 100 A were evaluated. To determine whether adding an air-gap (via Kapton tape layers) can mitigate saturation without degrading performance, an affordable and accurate test setup for assessing probe linearity and saturation limits was developed. A specialized test fixture given in Fig. 37 was designed enabling both frequency response and non-linearity measurements.

Fig. 37. Specialized test fixture

Two Tekbox probes (TBCP5-150k400 and TBCP2-250) were tested. Variable air-gaps (50–600 μm) were introduced by Kapton film between ferrite halves. Low-frequency bias currents were applied via additional windings or bias-tee circuits. To minimize measurement noise, a 9th-order passive Chebyshev low-pass filter was developed, improving the generator’s signal purity by >60 dB for the 2nd harmonic. Measurements were conducted using a Vector Network Analyzer and a Spectrum Analyzer (SA) for frequency response and harmonic distortion analysis, respectively.

Fig. 38. Application of Kapton film in the TBCP5 airgap.

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Key Findings on the increased air gap application are listed below:

- Frequency Response: Increasing the air-gap causes a predictable shift of the low-frequency corner, slightly reducing low-frequency sensitivity but leaving the flat-band response unchanged.
- With 200–300 μm air-gap, probes maintained stable frequency response up to 100 A DC bias, exceeding their nominal saturation current (80 A).
- Distortion Tests: Harmonic by-products were below the measurement noise floor (≈ -100 dBc), confirming negligible non-linearity even at high bias currents.
- The added air-gap effectively prevented magnetic saturation without deteriorating transfer impedance or bandwidth, demonstrating a practical enhancement method.

In Fig. 39 (a) nominal frequency response of the TBCP5 probe was given and in Fig. 39 (b), results of comparison with increased air-gap thickness are given in Fig. 40, 0 A and 100A responses with air-gap of 200 μm and 300 μm are presented.

Fig. 39. TBCP5 frequency response (a) nominal (as per datasheet) (b) with increasing air-gap thickness (from 50 μm to 600 μm of Kapton)

Fig. 40. Preliminary results of the TBCP5 frequency response under 0 and 100 A with air-gap of (a) 200 μm and (b) 300 μm .

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Consequently, RF current probes retain excellent linearity and minimal distortion up to 100 A with minor air-gap modification. Introducing a controlled air-gap is a low-cost and effective strategy to extend probe dynamic range and prevent saturation in high-current EMC applications the proposed measurement setup enables accurate testing of probe performance under realistic load conditions, aligning with CISPR 16-1-2 requirements.

2.7 Compact Impedance Measurement Device

Based on (6)-(9), a portable live impedance measurement system was designed, developed and validated, which incorporates an Omicron Bode 100 VNA and two home-made internal current probes, supporting also the use of external probes by means of internal RF switches given in Fig. 41.

The overall dimensions are 43 cm (L) × 28 cm (W) × 15 cm (H) with a weight of about 6 kg, which make the system portable. The portable system is connected to a PC through a USB port. A software solution was also developed in C language using the LabWindows™/CVI platform to operate the device and collect data in tabular and graphical form. The two tabs of the main window are shown in Fig. 42. The software is able to control the portable device, perform live impedance measurements through S parameters for short, open, reference and unknown impedance conditions and to ultimately calculate magnitude and phase of the unknown impedance along including cable impedance values.

Fig. 41 Design of the portable impedance measurement system (a) high-level diagram, (b) photo

The portable system was verified against an Agilent E5061B VNA with the 2-probe setup of Fig. 13, using a set of known/unknown impedances: Rosenberger 50 Ω N-type termination, Maury 2561C mismatch termination **Hata! Başvuru kaynağı bulunamadı.**, 150 Ω coupling-decoupling network and 100 pF capacitor.

The results for two selected tests (the 50 Ω reference and the mismatched termination) are shown in Fig. 42 for both magnitude and phase of the unknown impedance Z_x measured from 10 kHz to 30 MHz. In general performance is worse at the right end of the frequency interval, but also at low frequency for worse performance especially of the VNA directional couplers. Looking at Fig. 43 (c,d) a larger dispersion at low frequency may be seen, probably due to the limited performance of the Bode 100 emerging when tested with a mismatch standard. The performance of the Bode 100 internal probes (orange) is slightly better than when using external probes (blue), but definitely worse than the reference Agilent VNA E5061B provided by SIQ.

Further tests were carried out to verify (i) the non-linearity of the probes approaching supposed saturation values for the linked ampere-turns, and (ii) the effect of a deteriorated signal-to-noise ratio due to added external noise.

The test setup was built around the two-probe setup shown in Fig. 13, adding a 42-turn coil to drive a large bias current into the probes (“bias coil”) and a 3-turn coil to apply an arbitrary amount of noise by means of a function generator (“noise coil”). The probes selected for the tests were the two probes with the largest saturation point available and of different construction, so with quite a different size and probe factor: FCC-73 **Hata! Başvuru kaynağı bulunamadı.** and EZ-17 **Hata! Başvuru kaynağı bulunamadı.**

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The geometry of the bias coil was the result of a trade-off between opposing requisites: (i) compactness to fit into the probes window, (ii) large number of turns to reduce the amount of externally fed bias current, and (iii) self-resonance due to unavoidable stray capacitance. The first two requisites were relatively easy to handle finding a compromise in the built 42 turns. The third requisite instead turned out to be unmanageable by design, as a self-resonance was always present in the frequency range of interest (9 kHz to 30 MHz, even down to 2 kHz). It was decided to include the bias coil in the setup during the calibration with care of terminating it exactly in the same feeding conditions when bias current is applied. To this aim not only the connection, but the output impedance of the power supplies turned out to be relevant. The same was repeated for the noise coil having connected the function generator turned on, but at negligible output signal.

Frequency (Hz)	Unknown Impedance Mag (Ohm)	Unknown Impedance Angle (Radian)	Overall Loop Impedance Mag (Ohm)	Overall Loop Impedance Angle (Radian)	Setup Impedance Mag (Ohm)	Setup Impedance Angle (Radian)
150000	68,00074	0,66883	69,41044	0,674951	1,471097	0,961842
160000	70,43525	0,648522	71,87723	0,655541	1,526017	0,985464
170000	72,49498	0,627926	73,9663	0,63586	1,581875	1,007979
180000	74,42241	0,607412	75,92027	0,616241	1,638315	1,028937
190000	76,34808	0,587632	77,87124	0,597323	1,696568	1,048563
200000	77,82625	0,568605	79,37267	0,579177	1,755529	1,066977
300000	87,64107	0,423034	89,35024	0,441665	2,374681	1,199756
400000	92,11189	0,334702	93,91993	0,360742	3,022339	1,277294

(a) (b)

Fig. 42. Screenshots of the software developed for the live impedance measurements with the portable device (a) measurement parameters, (b) measurement results.

(a) (b)

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Fig. 43. Verification of the portable system performance vs. the Agilent E5061B VNA for (a,b) Rosemberg 50 Ω reference and (c,d) Maury mismatch reference.

2.8 Bias current effect and saturation

The tested bias current values were 2, 3, 4 and 5 A DC (that multiplied by 42 turns bring to 84, 126, 168 and 210 At), applied in turn to each of the two probes. The results consist of measured impedance curves referred to the 50 Ω calibration standard for the conditions of “no bias current applied” and the various bias current levels previously listed. In the case of the FCC 73, due to its large gain, it was judged opportune to add a test level at lower current, namely 1A.

The results can be seen in Fig. 44 and Fig. 45. The effect of the bias current is more pronounced at lower frequency, being negligible at higher frequency. It is likely that this results, or is at least promoted, by the Bode 100 VNA lower dynamic range, which makes it more susceptible to current probes non-linear behaviour. The effect of bias current below saturation point on impedance measurements can be minimal if the dynamic range of the VNA is sufficiently large (this is a point to check in order to define a requirement on the instrumentation to use).

2.9 External noise and reduced signal-to-noise ratio

The noise coil was instead fed with 1.0, 3.2, 6.0 and 10.0 Vpp of white noise amplitude, with the generator set for white noise over the bandwidth up to 30 MHz. An offline calculation was carried out to estimate the power spectral density and to compare with spectra measured with the E5061B, finding a very good correspondence. The 1 Vpp level led to no visible effect, for which during post-processing only the results of the 3 largest levels were retained and are displayed in the following.

It is evident that at high frequency the largest effect is caused by the largest noise applied (10 Vpp). The situation is more confused below 100 kHz, where in some instances the reference case seems the one with the largest spread. This disordered behaviour may still be caused by the lower performance at low frequency of the Bode 100 compared to a full-fledged laboratory VNA. That’s why the measurement system was then equipped with an RF amplifier in order to solve this low frequency problem.

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Fig. 44. Impedance curves of the 50 Ω reference vs. bias current for the EZ-17: (a) magnitude, (b) phase.

Fig. 45. Impedance curves of the 50 Ω reference vs. bias current for the FCC-73: (a) magnitude, (b) phase.

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Fig. 46. Impedance curves of the 50 Ω reference vs. external noise for the FCC-73: (a) magnitude, (b) phase.

A paper on development of the compact impedance measurement device was published in EMC Europe 2024 Conference [52].

3. Uncertainty

3.1 Evaluation of uncertainty contribution from Artificial Mains Networks (AMNs)

One of the uncertainty contributors to the conducted emission measurements in standard conditions is AMN. In this context, to help the users of CISPR standards, a software was developed to calculate the AMN impedance and the uncertainty contribution of LISNs to conducted emission results.

The specifications of the commercial AMNs are given in CISPR 16-1-2 [53]. There are two prominent types of AMNs defined in CISPR 16-1-2 to cover the frequency range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz; the 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω AMN from 9 kHz to 150 kHz and the 50 Ω / 50 μH AMN from 150 kHz to 30 MHz. In CISPR 16-1-2, the tolerance of the impedance is specified. Boundaries are given for the magnitude with ± 20 % and for the phase with ±11.5° across the whole frequency band. This means that the tolerance is accounted an annulus sector around the nominal impedance as seen in Fig. 47. It is assumed that both boundaries are not independent from each other as per CISPR 16-4-2 [2, 54-56]. On the other hand, there seems to have been an ambiguity between the specification in CISPR 16-1-2 and the impact of the tolerance given in CISPR 16-4-2. A rectangular tolerance sector (independently ± 20 % for the magnitude and ± 11.5° for the phase) appears to be defined in CISPR 16-1-2 whereas the calculation of the impact is based on a tolerance circle (dependently ± 20 % for the magnitude and ± 11.5° for the phase as seen in Fig. 46) in CISPR 16-4-2. In fact, this is interpreted in a different manner by some people, also by many calibration laboratories and AMN manufacturers, as follows because of this ambiguity; the annular tolerance in CISPR 16-4-2 is only for defining nominal AMN uncertainty component δZ_{AN} which is used to calculate U_{CISPR} in CISPR 16-4-2 for conducted emission tests. Having an AMN impedance uncertainty value (δZ_{AMN}) larger than δZ_{AN} will only mean a higher uncertainty contribution to the overall expanded test uncertainty but does not mean the AMN cannot be used for testing as long as the CISPR16-1-2 magnitude limits are met. If the CISPR 16-1-2 magnitude limits are exceeded, that signifies the AMN cannot be used for testing and must be fixed before placing it in use. Nevertheless, exceeding phase limits is tolerable and it is evaluated in the uncertainty calculation. As a result of all, due to the aforementioned ambiguity, it might be deduced that CISPR 16-1-2 states independent

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magnitude and phase tolerances for checking the AMN adequacy while CISPR 16-4-2 states dependent and annular magnitude and phase tolerances for particularly defining U_{CISPR} . In the scope of this paper, δZ_{AN} will denote the uncertainty component in CISPR 16-4-2 for U_{CISPR} calculation whereas δZ_{AMN} will denote the uncertainty component that results from an actual AMN used in emission testing.

Fig. 47. Definition of impedance magnitude and phase tolerances [2, 54-56].

A piece of software was developed which presents more options and features in comparison to the software solutions in literature. In fact, there is a useful software solution in literature in [56] to calculate the AMN uncertainty contribution but is limited to a number of AMNs and for one frequency at a time. Our developed software allows AMN circuit definition and subsequently calculates nominal impedance magnitude & phase information seen by the EUT along with the nominal AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AN}) which is used for U_{CISPR} calculation and based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2. Additionally, the same software calculates the actual AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) to be directly placed in the uncertainty calculation budget of an actual emission test when impedance magnitude and phase values in an actual AMN calibration report taken from a calibration laboratory are entered into the software. Following this, we performed AMN impedance uncertainty analysis for most commonly used AMN types.

In CISPR 16-4-2 a worst case analysis is performed to get the measurement error. The calculation is based on the work of [8], which uses reflection coefficients normalized to system impedance $Z_o = 50$ as given in (22) to (24) [54, 56];

$$\Gamma_{NOM} = \frac{Z_{NOM} - Z_o}{Z_{NOM} + Z_o} \quad (22)$$

$$\Gamma_{AMN} = \frac{Z_{AMN} - Z_o}{Z_{AMN} + Z_o} \quad (23)$$

$$\Gamma_{EUT} = \frac{Z_{EUT} - Z_o}{Z_{EUT} + Z_o} = \rho \exp(j\phi) \quad (24)$$

The voltages are derived by using (2) to (4) as given in (5) and (6);

$$V_{NOM} = \frac{Z_{NOM}}{Z_{EUT} + Z_{NOM}} V_{EUT} \quad (25)$$

$$V_{AMN} = \frac{Z_{AMN}}{Z_{EUT} + Z_{AMN}} V_{EUT} \quad (26)$$

The measurement error is calculated using (7);

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$$\Delta U = 20 \log \left(\left| \frac{1 + \Gamma_{AMN}}{1 - \Gamma_{AMN}} \frac{1 - \Gamma_{NOM} \Gamma_{EUT}}{1 + \Gamma_{NOM}} \right| \right) \quad (27)$$

Due to the impedance specification, Z_{AMN} with a tolerance circle is calculated by (8). It is assumed that the worst case will occur if Z_{AMN} is exactly on this circle and not inside the circle. Consequently, in (4), $\rho = 1$ and $|\Gamma_{EUT}|$ is assumed to be 1 [4, 6].

$$Z_{AMN} = Z_{NOM} + 0.2|Z_{NOM}|e^{j\theta} \quad (28)$$

$$0 \leq \theta < 2\pi \quad (29)$$

All possible combinations of φ and θ were used with 0.5 degrees steps in (24) and (28) in the analysis. The software window developed in the scope of this study is presented in Fig. 4 (a) along with the most general AMN circuit diagram in Fig. 48 (b) analyzed by the software. As depicted in Fig. 4 (a), the software allows the definition of AMNs in a large scale by entering the required AMN circuit component values on the AMN circuit and subsequently produces nominal AMN impedance (Z_{NOM}) seen from the EUT and based on the entered values. It also accepts the actual AMN impedance magnitude and phase values (Z_{AMN}) taken from a calibration laboratory. At the end, while it produces the AMN impedance nominal values (Z_{NOM}) seen from the EUT as depicted in Fig. 48 (b), it also produces uncertainty contribution δZ_{AMN} for the actual AMN impedance, obtained from a AMN calibration laboratory, along with the nominal AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AN}) which is based on the annular tolerance and used for U_{CISPR} calculation as per CISPR 16-4-2. The software additionally allows adjusting the annular impedance magnitude tolerance, if requested, from the 20 % default value to any desired value for special analyses, and changing the 0.5° default φ and θ step in order to increase and decrease the depth of the analysis.

(a)

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(b)

Fig. 48. (a) Software window for AMN impedance and uncertainty calculation, (b) the most general AMN diagram used in the software.

In the scope of the project, we studied the commonly used AMN types whose circuits are given in Fig. 49 – Fig. 52. As seen in Fig. 49 – Fig. 52, depending on the related standard, the AMNs have slight or significant variations in design and components between them. When we examine the circuitry of the AMNs more carefully, we see that the CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω & CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH combination, MIL-STD-461 50μH, ANSI C63.4 [57] AMNs are fundamentally similar apart from some minor components & values. For that reason, we selected the MIL-STD-461G 50μH AMN along with CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω & CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH AMN combination for analysis to represent this AMN group. Likewise, the MIL-STD-461G 5 μH, CISPR 25 [58], and DO-160G [59] AMNs are similar and we selected the MIL-STD-461G 5 μH AMN for analysis to represent this second group. However, as ISO 7637-2 [60] and ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C [61] AMNs are markedly different in terms of circuitry and analysis results, we analyzed each of them separately. As a consequence, for each selected AMN type, we calculated nominal impedance magnitude & phase impedance curves and δZ_{AN} stated in CISPR16-4-2 for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the tolerance circle shown in Fig. 46. In this study, regardless of the relevant standards of the studied AMNs, all the AMN types were analyzed in the same configuration with the following parameters for consistency; the short-circuit and open-circuit source impedance conditions, the frequency range of 9 kHz - 400 MHz that reflects the widest AMN frequency range considering most of the AMN-related standards, and annular 20 % magnitude & $\pm 11.5^\circ$ phase tolerance. In fact, the treatment of the source side differs from one standard to another during impedance calibration. For instance, the open-circuit condition is demanded for ANSI C63.4, MIL-STD-461, DO-160G while the short circuit condition is for CISPR 25, ISO 11452-2. Both of the conditions have good arguments; the short-circuit condition may signify the theoretical correct treatment of a voltage source whereas the open-circuit condition may denote that the source side of the AMN is connected to the source with a cable. From an RF perspective the impedance of this cable is high due to the inductance of the cable. Additionally, it is practical in calibration with the open-circuit condition since no additional adapter is required.

Our prominent aim was to show the usability of the software in any desired configuration even different from the configurations stated in the related AMN standards, if required. In addition, independently of the relevant standards of the analysed AMN types & their related frequency ranges, it was aimed to set out the results in the entire frequency range (9 kHz – 400 MHz) per AMN. Therefore, readers can also have the chance of seeing the full picture of the entire range which is not shown in the relevant AMN standards.

In this context, we firstly produced nominal impedance values and δZ_{AN} , which is stated in CISPR16-4-2 for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the tolerance circle, for the AMN by using the developed software. Thereafter, we used one of our actual AMNs and its calibration certificate taken from a calibration laboratory in an attempt to calculate the actual AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) to be placed into the uncertainty budget of the CE102 test. Although phase information is not stipulated by the standard for military AMNs, we requested the phase information from the calibration laboratory along with the magnitude information particularly for this research. Consequently, the actual AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) was calculated to be used in CE102 uncertainty budget.

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Fig. 49. CISPR 16-1-2 ideal AMN diagrams excerpted from the standard (a) 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω, (b) 50 Ω / 50 μH.

Fig. 50. MIL-STD-461G AMN (a) 50 μH, (b) 5 μH.

Fig. 51. Automotive test AMNs as per (a) ISO 7637-2, (b) CISPR 25.

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(c)

Fig. 52. Other reputable AMN types (a) DO-160G, (b) ANSI C63.4, (c) ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C.

The nominal impedance magnitude and phase values of the most commonly used AMNs, which were calculated by the developed software, are presented in Fig. 53 (a) – Fig. 57 (a). Additionally, δZ_{AN} values based on the annular tolerance in accordance with CISPR 16-4-2 are given in Fig. 53 (b) – Fig. 57 (b) and Table 4 with the obtained peak values. The second column of Table I shows the maximum and minimum AMN voltage deviations in the range of 9 kHz – 400 MHz which is deemed as the widest AMN frequency range in this research regardless of the AMN’s relevant standards, whereas the third column shows the values particularly in the frequency range stated in the standard where the relevant AMN is defined.

Regarding the CISPR AMNs, the combination of CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω & CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μH AMNs is very usable from 9 kHz as given in Fig. 52 based on the aforementioned annular tolerance and its magnitude & phase results are completely compatible with the standard tables given in CISPR 16-1-2. It should be noted that the CISPR AMNs analyzed in this paper are ideal AMNs in their simplest form as excerpted from the standard (see Fig. 48). Ultimately, ISO 7637-2 and ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMNs show their intrinsic behavior in magnitude, phase and δZ_{AN} curves as seen in Fig. 53 – Fig. 56 for both the short-circuit and open-circuit source impedance conditions. The ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMN seems to show the worst performance and become usable beyond 2 MHz for both of the source impedance conditions as seen in Fig. 55 – Fig. 56 based on the same annular tolerance given in CISPR 16-4-2. Nevertheless, it should be stressed that the ECSS AMN is not intended to measure the disturbance voltage and the disturbance current is measured with a current probe in the standard. Here, an answer is sought to the question “what happens if an ECSS AMN is used in conducted emission tests?”. As a result, it looks that the ECSS AMN is not suitable at all for the use in conducted emission tests considering the CISPR 16-4-2 tolerances. When we examine the ISO 7637-2 AMN results in Fig. 53 – Fig. 54, we see at the first glance that there is significant difference between the short-circuit and open-circuit source impedance condition results. The impedance magnitude curve for the open-circuit source impedance is utterly incompatible with the curve given in the standard whereas there is good agreement with the standard for the short-circuit power source case as the ISO 7637-2 requires the source side is short-circuited in calibration. However, the voltage deviation is remarkably high below 1 MHz for the short-circuit source impedance condition while the severity of the deviation is alleviated for the open-circuit source impedance condition and seems to be usable beyond 50 kHz in terms of voltage deviation. In fact, for ISO 7637-2 the magnitude tolerance is only 10 %, but the 20 % / 11.5° annular tolerance from CISPR is implemented here in this paper just for information and for making it comparable to the other analysed AMNs. When the overall results are evaluated together, the best performance is shown by the ANSI C63.4 AMN independently of source impedance conditions in the entire frequency range in accordance with Table 4 based on the annular tolerance of CISPR 16-4-2.

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Fig. 53. Combination of CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω (9 kHz – 150 kHz) & CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH (150 kHz – 400 MHz) AMNs (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 54. ISO 7637-2 AMN (R_s : open-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude – and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 55. ISO 7637-2 AMN (R_s : short-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

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Fig. 56. ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMN (R_S : open-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 57. ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMN (R_S : short-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Table 4. Nominal AMN uncertainty component δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation by AMN types based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2 in the range of 9 kHz – 400 MHz and specifically in the relevant AMN standard ranges.

AMN Type	CISPR 16-4-2 δZ_{AN} (dB) (9 kHz – 400 MHz)	CISPR 16-4-2 δZ_{AN} (dB) (AMN's standard frequency range)
CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μ H + 5 Ω (9 kHz – 150 kHz) & CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μ H (150 kHz – 400 MHz)	3.59 / -3.07	3.59 / -3.07 (9 kHz – 30 MHz)
ISO 7637-2 (RS : open-circuit)	11.31 / -5.24	1.70 / -2.01 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
ISO 7637-2 (Rs : short-circuit)	53.07 / -18.76	53.07 / -13.53 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)

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CISPR 25 (Rs : open-circuit)	45.42 / -21.06	45.42 / -16.02 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
CISPR 25 (Rs : short-circuit)	49.99 / -18.89	41.48 / -13.31 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
DO-160G (RS : open-circuit)	46.35 / -26.02	46.35 / -26.02 (10 kHz – 400 MHz)
DO-160G (Rs : short-circuit)	49.99 / -18.89	49.99 / -18.89 (10 kHz – 400 MHz)
ANSI C63.4 (RS : open-circuit)	3.33 / -2.94	3.33 / -2.94 (9 kHz – 30 MHz)
ANSI C63.4 (Rs : short-circuit)	3.31 / -2.93	3.31 / -2.93 (9 kHz – 30 MHz)
ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C (RS : open-circuit)	49.87 / -12.29	49.87 / -10.33 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C (Rs : short-circuit)	48.15 / -10.88	48.15 / -10.88 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)

Besides, although the voltage deviations seem to be very high and unacceptable in both the two and third columns of Table 4 for some AMNs, this should be reiterated here that all the analysis in Table 4 is based on the 20 % / 11.5° annular tolerance of CISPR16-4-2 irrelevant of the related standards of the analysed AMNs, which means that the uncertainty contribution arising from these AMNs can be reduced by choosing AMNs with a lower impedance tolerance for conducted emission tests. When a calibration report for an AMN is received from a calibration laboratory, it can be checked through the developed software. However, as studied above, the way of the AMN source side termination could have a significant effect on the AMN impedance, especially in the low frequency range and users should be cautious about it.

The developed software is a solution which will allow laboratories to calculate their own AMN uncertainty contribution (δZ_{AMN}) for any desired AMN type based on its actual LISN calibration certificate. The software also can calculate the nominal AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AN}) which is used to calculate U_{CISPR} as per CISPR 16-4-2 for any AMN type for a standard annular tolerance or a customized one. The analysis made by using the developed software clearly demonstrated how essential the specification of the phase is and consequently all conducted emission related standards which use AMNs should specify a phase tolerance to avoid going unchecked in terms of measurement uncertainty. Even this definition should be frequency-dependent as much as possible because much lower tolerance might be required in low frequencies for a suppressed uncertainty contribution. Ultimately, it was shown that both of the ways of the AMN source side termination, namely the open and short circuit conditions, should be particularly defined for the LISN impedance as significant difference might occur between them as reported in this paper and users should be aware of the risks even if the related standards define the impedance and/or phase requirements only for one of them.

Finally, the developed software is free to download on the following repository <https://zenodo.org/records/11229783>.

Uncertainty contribution of AMNs to conducted emission was published in IEEE EMC Magazine [62].

3.2 Uncertainty calculation of the new conducted emission method

In this section, uncertainty of the newly developed conducted emission method is evaluated. To enhance the measurement uncertainty evaluation, impedance and emission values were obtained with at least three succeeding measurements by observing the repeatability.

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The model function is determined according to CISPR 16-4-2 [2] and the uncertainty value for $V_{\text{calculated}}$ for this alternative conducted emission test is calculated as follows;

$$V_{\text{calculated}} = Z_{\text{AMN}} + I_{\text{corrected}} = Z_{\text{AMN}} + V_r + A_{\text{CP}} + \delta Z + \delta \text{CP} + \delta Y_{\text{Tf}} + \delta Z_{\text{CP}} + \delta M + \delta V_{\text{SW}} + \delta V_{\text{pr}} + \delta V_{\text{pa}} + \text{CL}$$

Where,

V_r is measuring device reading

Z_{AMN} is impedance of artificial mains network

A_{CP} is uncertainty of attenuation current probe – receiver

δZ is uncertainty of impedance measurement and established link to standard method

δCP is uncertainty of current probe transfer admittance factor

δY_{Tf} is uncertainty of transfer admittance frequency interpolation

δZ_{CP} is uncertainty of current probe insertion impedance

δM is effect of mismatch current monitor probe-receiver

δV_{SW} is receiver error due to sine wave voltage

δV_{pr} is receiver error due to pulse repetition response

δV_{pa} is receiver error due to pulse amplitude response

CL is uncertainty of cable loss

R is repeatability of measurement system

Table 5. Uncertainty calculation of new conducted emission method

Component symbol	Input Quantity	Units	Value +/-	Probability Distribution	Divisor	Ci	Ui (dB)
V_r	Receiver reading	dB	0,2	Rectangular	1,73	1	0,12
Z_{AMN}	impedance of artificial mains network	dB	0,5	Rectangular	1,73	1	0,29
ACP	Attenuation current probe – receiver	dB	0,2	Normal	2	1	0,10
dZ	Impedance measurement and established link to standard method	dB	1,6	Rectangular	1,73	1	0,92
dCP	Current monitor probe admittance factor	dB	1,0	Normal	2	1	0,50

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dY _{Tf}	Transfer admittance frequency interpolation	dB	0,1	Rectangular	1,73	1	0,06
dZ _{CP}	Current monitor insertion impedance	dB	0,1	Rectangular	1,73	1	0,06
dM	Mismatch current monitor probe – EMI Receiver	dB	0,8	U Shape	1,41	1	0,57
dV _{SW}	Receiver sine wave voltage	dB	1,0	Normal	2	1	0,50
dV _{pr}	Receiver pulse repetition rate response	dB	2,0	Rectangular	1,73	1	1,16
dV _{pa}	Receiver pulse Amplitude response	dB	2,0	Rectangular	1,73	1	1,16
CL	Cable loss	dB	0,2	Normal	2	1	0,10
R	Repeatability	dB	1,6	Normal	1	1	1,60
U _c	Combined uncertainty			Normal			3,09

Taking a confidence interval of 95% (k=2) for the expanded uncertainty:

$$U = 2 U_c = 6,18 \text{ dB}$$

In the project, aimed uncertainty is 6 dB.

4. Conclusion

The experimental results support the effectiveness of the proposed method for low frequency emission, that is, low frequency emission testing can be significantly improved throughout live impedance measurements. When the loop impedance and current values are known for a certain test site, the measured emission levels, namely the loop current, can be estimated for other sites/conditions as long as the loop impedance is also known at that targeted site. Alternatively, emission results obtained in different test environments may be scaled to a defined impedance value, such as 50 Ω, to harmonise emission results obtained from different test environments and make them comparable. Even a standard limit corresponding to the defined impedance can be determined for standardisation and source impedance-independent test results.

Another improvement in this study, the two probe impedance measurement is enhanced to cover the full 100 Hz–150 kHz frequency range, enabling in-situ measurement of harmonics (100 Hz–2 kHz), and supraharmonics (2 kHz–150 kHz), using high-amperage current probes. To achieve reliable correlation between laboratory and in-situ conditions, the method is improved by integrating an amplifier with a low-cost mini VNA—making the approach accessible and cost-effective. Then, correlation factors were established between the grid impedance and a standard 50-ohm LISN impedance. This factor can be applied to in-situ current measurements, allowing emissions to be estimated in voltage units and compared against limits in any standard. Moreover, by using time-domain measurement techniques in 150 kHz–30 MHz range, both amplitude and phase information are obtained, reducing uncertainty in the measurement results.

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Additionally, since the in-situ measurements are sometimes due to high current conditions of the EUT, saturation performance of current probes are evaluated. Then a method to increase the current handling of clamp-on probes was proposed.

In accordance with the impedance measurement method, a compact impedance measurement device which can be used in harsh environments was developed and constructed. The device can be used in AMN impedance verifications in laboratories and in in-situ emission measurements method proposed in this document as well.

Finally, uncertainty calculation of the new emission measurement method and AMN uncertainty contribution to the conducted emission tests are evaluated.

Harsh environment impedance measurements can be found in <https://zenodo.org/records/17366415>.

In conclusion, Deliverable 1 of EMC-STD project has been successfully achieved and this document meets the objective 1 requirements committed in Annex 1 JRP Protocol. This report will be submitted to CISPR/CIS/B WG7 along with all other project findings and deliverables at the WG7 meeting (next meeting as of the end of this project) in Berlin, Germany, on 8th – 10th April 2026.

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